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● Two newly recorded genera and two newly recorded species of Cerambycidae in Chongqing Municipality

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Abstract: This paper presents the first records of two cerambycid genera and their corresponding species in Chongqing Municipality, southwestern China. The newly recorded genera include *Paruraecha* Breuning, 1935 and *Thermistis* Pascoe, 1867. The corresponding newly recorded species are *Paruraecha submarmorata* (Gressitt, 1936) and *Thermistis croceocincta* (Saunders, 1839).

Keywords: Longicorn beetles, new records, taxonomy

● 重庆市天牛科二新纪录属二新纪录种

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摘要: 本文首次报道了重庆市天牛科两个新纪录属及其相应的两个新纪录种。两个新纪录属为肖泥色天牛属 *Paruraecha* Breuning, 1935 和刺楔天牛属 *Thermistis* Pascoe, 1867。两个新纪录种为台湾肖泥色天牛 *Paruraecha submarmorata* (Gressitt, 1936) 和刺楔天牛 *Thermistis croceocincta* (Saunders, 1839)。

关键词: 天牛, 新纪录, 分类学

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● Introduction

The Jinfoshan National Nature Reserve is located in Nanchuan District, Chongqing Municipality, China, lies in the transitional zone between the southeastern edge of the Sichuan Basin and the Yunnan-Guizhou Plateau. It is renowned for its remarkable biodiversity and serves as a vital gene bank for biological species in China.

From May 2022 to August 2024, the authors conducted a comprehensive survey of longhorn beetles in the Jinfoshan National Nature Reserve. This investigation revealed two newly recorded genera and their corresponding species within the subfamily Lamiinae for Chongqing Municipality, which are recorded as follows.

● Material and methods

All habitus photographs were taken with a Canon 5D Mark II digital camera equipped with a Canon EF 100mm f/2.8L IS USM lens. All photographs were edited using Adobe Photoshop CC.

The materials examined for this study also referenced the works of Hua *et al.* (2009) and Lin & Tavakilian (2019). The specimens are deposited in the Insect Collection, College of Agriculture, Yangtze University, Jingzhou, Hubei, China (YZU).

● Taxonomy

Subfamily Lamiinae Latreille, 1825

Genus *Paruraecha* Breuning, 1935 肖泥色天牛属

Paruraecha Breuning, 1935: 64; Gressitt 1951: 383; Lin & Tavakilian 2019: 317.

Type species. *Paruraecha szetschuanica* Breuning, 1935.

Distribution. China, India.

Remarks. This genus comprises 4 species within 2 subgenera, with 3 species distributed in China. One species, *Paruraecha submarmorata* (Gressitt, 1936) was newly found in Chongqing.

Paruraecha submarmorata (Gressitt, 1936) 台湾肖泥色天牛

Fig. 1a

Arisania submarmorata Gressitt, 1936: 107.

Paruraecha submarmorata: Gressitt 1951: 384.

Material examined. 1♀, China: Chongqing, Jinfoshan, Nanmuwan (楠木湾), E 107°9'22"N 29°12'58"Alt. 1288m, May 13, 2024, Liang Zhang leg.

Diagnosis. Body mostly black, with antennae, elytra and legs dark reddish-brown. Head densely and uniformly covered with orange-yellow pubescence; antennae clothed with pale gray pubescence from base of antennomere 3 onward; pronotum unevenly clothed with orange-yellow pubescence forming irregular patches; elytra mostly clothed with orange-yellow pubescence, denser at basal and apical two-fifths forming irregular patches, rather sparse at middle interspersed with denser patches of light gray pubescence; disc provided with two faintly visible longitudinal ridges; apex rounded.

It differs from the similar species, *Paruraecha acutipennis* (Gressitt, 1942), in having the rounded elytral apex, while in the latter species, the elytral apex is obliquely and concavely truncated.

Distribution: China (Chongqing, Shaanxi, Zhejiang, Taiwan).

FIGURE 1. **a** *Paruraecha submarmorata* (Gressitt, 1936) **b** *Thermistis croceocincta* (Saunders, 1839).

Genus *Thermistis* Pascoe, 1867 刺楔天牛属

Thermistis Pascoe, 1867: 438; Gressitt 1951: 562; Lin *et al.* 2012: 30; Lin & Tavakilian 2019: 404.

Type species. *Lamia croceocincta* Saunders, 1839.

Distribution. China, Vietnam, Laos, Thailand, India, Myanmar.

Remarks. This genus comprises 12 species, all of which are distributed in China, with one species, *Thermistis croceocincta* (Saunders, 1839) newly found in Chongqing.

Thermistis croceocincta (Saunders, 1839) 刺楔天牛

Fig. 1b

Lamia croceocincta Saunders, 1839: 178.

Thermistis croceocincta: Pascoe 1867: 439.

Thermistis apicalis Pic, 1923: 14.

Thermistes croceocincta var. *rufobasalis* Pic 1950: 13.

Thermistis croceocincta m. *apicalis*: Breuning 1966: 729.

Thermistis croceocincta m. *rufovasalis*: Breuning 1966: 729.

Thermistis croceocincta apicalis: Nara & Yu 1992 133, figs. 1.6, 1.7.

Thermistis croceocincta croceocincta: Hubweber *et al.* 2010: 332.

Material examined. 1♂, China: Chongqing, Jinfoshan, West Chenjiawan (西陈家湾), 107°4'51"E, 29°3'13"N, Alt. 645m, May 27, 2023, Jia-Ling Chen leg.

Diagnosis. Body black, with frons and most of ventral surface densely clothed with yellow pubescence. Antennae deep black, each antennomere provided with a narrow grayish-white pubescent rings at base and apex. Pronotum provided with a yellow pubescent patch on each side of anterior margin. Each elytron provided with three yellow transverse pubescent bands: the basal one transverse, after scutellum, the middle one oblique, usually behind middle, the apical one at apex. Legs black, with femora often covered with thin yellow pubescence.

It differs from its closest congener, *Thermistis hainanensis* Lin & Yang, 2012, in having the elytral middle black marking extended to epipleuron, while in the latter species, the black marking does not extend to the epipleuron.

Distribution. China (Chongqing, Shaanxi, Anhui, Zhejiang, Hubei, Jiangxi, Hunan, Fujian, Guangdong, Hainan, Hong Kong, Guangxi, Sichuan, Guizhou, Yunnan), India, Vietnam, Thailand.

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● Additional information

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